

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH GAMES

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Annotation

In the process of learning English in a playful way, the teacher can use any opportunity: drawing, playing with dolls and soldiers, modeling from plasticize, active outdoor games. This approach is better than learning the language from textbooks, but it is worth paying attention to how it is perceived by children. If the level of self-discipline allows not only to play, but also to learn the subject, then this method can be successfully used.

Key words

Teaching English; Teaching Technique; Foreign Language; Games; Language Games

Nowadays English is becoming weightier. Teaching English to the youngsters is complicated because English is not their mother tongue and it is a new thing for them. The teacher should have a skillful and an interesting technique to introduce English for them, so that the young learners will be interested and motivated to learn English. There are a lot of ways to familiarize English to the young learners.

Games and fun activities are a vital part of teaching English as a foreign language. Whether you're teaching adults or children, games will liven up your lesson and ensure that your learners will leave the classroom wanting more.

Games can be used to warm up the class before lesson begins, during the lesson to give learners a break when you're tackling a tough subject, or at the end of class when you have a few minutes left to kill. There are literally hundreds, probably thousands, of games that you can use to activate your students.

Games can be effectively used in various ways, such as for a quick review, after material has been covered or as a cool-down activity at the end of a lesson to practice what has been covered. You could also use a game to practice specific new aspects of language in groups or pairs for a limited time, as a short introduction to new vocabulary or a grammar rule, as a prompt for writing work, even as a link into a new part of the lesson. Games may even be used merely to change the pace of a lesson.

The use of games in the educational process has become widespread for a reason. This method has a number of advantages.

☒ Game exercises are a great way to change the type of activity and increase the attention of students.

☒ Games also help in additional practice of new lexical and grammatical structures. For example, role-playing situations on a certain topic helps to activate your knowledge and transform a passive vocabulary into an active one.

☒ In a game way, you can not only learn and consolidate new material, but also check what you have learned. For a teacher, this is a great chance to see how freely students can feel in various proposed communication situations, what typical mistakes they make, what vocabulary they have mastered, etc.

☒ Game techniques allow the teacher to get away from the monotonous and monotonous work in the classroom, turning boring cramming into an interesting and exciting learning process.

To sum up I can say one of the best solutions is through games which meet the purpose of creating a relaxing and motivating atmosphere for most learners and using interactive games in all English lessons promotes formation of a creative, active person, capable to change in the changing world.

Teaching is a wonderful profession, and one thing we all know is that we never forget our teachers. Instead, we vividly remember the few incredible teachers we had who challenged us and made us think rather than spoon-fed us so we could be successfully processed through exams like a sausage.

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